

Leave no one behind in the UN Ocean Decade

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Summary

Recent policy shifts terminating programs and funding related to diversity, equity, and inclusion challenge the 'leave no one behind' pledge at the core of the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science. We urge the Ocean Decade to build capacity and resilience to safeguard its inclusivity commitments at forthcoming UN ocean events.

Main text

Global ocean challenges such as biodiversity loss, marine pollution, overfishing, and climate change affect society at large, but disproportionately impact vulnerable groups—particularly women, Indigenous Peoples, youth, and coastal communities in the Global South—who remain underrepresented in ocean science and governance^{1,2}. The ocean plays a critical role in supporting the food and nutrition security of billions of people, with 1 in 14 people globally relying on seafood for subsistence, while 1 in 12, nearly half of them women, depend on small-scale fishing for their livelihoods³. Ocean-dependent communities are especially vulnerable to environmental changes, such as marine pollution¹ and climate-driven declines in nutritional yields from fisheries (~30% in low-income countries by 2100⁴). The United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (Ocean Decade, 2021–2030) is a transformative global effort to generate the knowledge and partnerships needed to ensure a sustainable and inclusive future for the ocean. Central to the [Ocean Decade's vision](#) is the pledge to “leave no one behind”, which underscores the importance of diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) in shaping a more just and effective global ocean science community⁵. However, [policies that terminate DEI-related programs and funding](#)

pose significant challenges to this agenda, disrupting global cooperation in ocean science and undermining progress towards the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Decisions made at the upcoming 2025 UN Ocean Conference (UNOC3) and the 33rd session of the General Assembly of UNESCO's Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) will shape the trajectory of the Ocean Decade towards 2030. In this context, we—294 ocean scientists spanning 45 countries and six continents—call on the Ocean Decade to use this pivotal moment to reaffirm its commitment to leaving no one behind. This commitment is central to realizing the full potential of the Ocean Decade and will ensure that its benefits are shared broadly and equitably.

Inclusivity is key to the UN Decade of Ocean Science

Evidence-based approaches are necessary to address global ocean challenges for the billions of people who depend on a healthy ocean for food and livelihoods. Despite growing recognition that DEI enhances the breadth and relevance of science (e.g., through global discussions, knowledge exchange, and policy engagement^{6,7}), ocean science remains one of the least diverse disciplines, with persistent gaps in recruitment, retention, and leadership opportunities for underrepresented groups⁸. Ensuring that all nations and communities can equitably participate in research, policy development, and international negotiations is not simply a matter of fairness; it is fundamental to the Ocean Decade's goal of co-producing knowledge for sustainable development.

The Ocean Decade was launched in response to urgent warnings from the First World Ocean Assessment, which highlighted the accelerating degradation of marine ecosystems and called for coordinated and sustainable solutions. It is guided by the IOC Member States, facilitated by the Decade Coordination Unit, and implemented with the support of partners including the Ocean Decade Alliance, National Decade Committees, and institutions leading endorsed Decade Actions.

Through this comprehensive network, the Ocean Decade has made meaningful strides toward generational, gender, and knowledge system diversity. In the [2024 Decade Progress Report](#), a significant proportion (32%) of the 23,000 individuals engaged in Ocean Decade Actions identified as early career professionals. While gender parity has not been reached with 42.5% of participants identifying as women and 48.6% men (remaining 8.9% not specified), further work to develop inclusive policies and a gender framework is on course through a dedicated [Gender Expert Working Group](#). Recognizing the importance of co-producing knowledge, the Decade has also developed [guiding principles](#) for an ethical and respectful approach to working with local knowledge holders and users.

Persistent gaps in equal representation and inclusivity

Geographic asymmetry remains high, with the United States (n = 115), Canada (n = 49), the United Kingdom (n = 47), France (n = 44), and China (n = 26) accounting for 43.4% of Decade Action lead institutions (648 [Decade Actions as of January 2025](#); Figure 1). Italy and the United States also have the highest proportion of Actions addressing Challenge 9 (skills, knowledge, technology, and participation for all). As a consequence of this geographic concentration, up to 1 in 3 global ocean science publications and 1 in 5 Decade Actions are vulnerable to anti-DEI policy-making (Table S1). In addition, Challenge 9 ranks third-lowest among the ten Challenges in terms of generated knowledge products. The overreliance of the Ocean Decade on a small number of countries is not a justification to scale back their investments, rather it highlights the need for concrete actions that promote geographic inclusion and capacity development that enhance the resilience to shifts on policy.

Figure 1. [Country-level contributions to the UN Ocean Decade](#). Contributions are measured by the number of Decade Action lead institutions per country. Breaks are created with the Fisher natural breaks algorithm. The first dimension represents the total number of Actions (breaks at 17 and 50; range = 1-116), while the second dimension represents the proportion of Actions focused on capacity development (“Challenge 9: Skills, knowledge, technology and participation for all”; breaks at 7 and 29; range = 1-67). Dark-gray areas indicate zero Actions.

Innovation, equitable participation, and societal uptake are all central to achieving SDG 14 (Life Below Water), but they may be limited by anti-DEI policies. Empirical data consistently link team diversity with greater innovation, creativity, and problem-solving capacity in science^{9,10}. These benefits are highly relevant to marine conservation, a field characterized by interdisciplinary and transboundary complexity. DEI initiatives also promote inclusive collaboration and equitable access to knowledge networks by engaging a wide range of voices and capacities that have historically been excluded^{6,10}. Human rights frameworks reinforce these efforts by emphasizing justice, recognition, and reconciliation with communities subject to historical and structural marginalization as essential components of ocean conservation^{11,12}. Including diverse and local perspectives enhances the legitimacy and social relevance of ocean science by enabling adaptive, context-specific solutions and increasing societal uptake, particularly when research is co-

produced with nations and vulnerable communities most affected by ocean change^{2,13}. Without focused attention to equity across development, climate adaptation, and conservation policy domains, there is a heightened risk of maladaptive actions and negative impacts on human health and well-being, which will exacerbate the vulnerability of marginalized communities and likely undermine joint policy goals¹⁴.

Risks are looming with anti-DEI policy shifts

Anti-DEI policy limits hiring, shifts funding priorities, and halts research and participatory practices, thereby [impeding international collaboration and science diplomacy](#). In ocean science, recent policy shifts threaten the integrity and continuity of international research programs through project closures, loss of expertise, and loss of long-term datasets essential to ocean research¹⁵. For example, the discontinuation of [long-term ocean observation, weather](#), and [climate-related disaster](#) data collection undermines international collaborations and evidence-based policy responses that produce knowledge necessary to ensure the safety and well-being of ocean-dependent communities. Once disrupted, scientific collaborations, networks, and infrastructure cannot be simply reinstated; rebuilding requires significant time and resources to restore social, financial, and institutional capacity.

Backsliding on the Ocean Decade's ambitions for reducing asymmetries in knowledge, skills, and access to technology is a growing risk. Among the 284 supporters of this paper (including 32 anonymous signatories; [Table S2 and S3](#)), 64 (~23%) reported direct impacts of anti-DEI policy-making on their work, including the inability to attend conferences, funding cuts, self-censoring, loss of shared shiptime, and the suspension of projects and collaborations. Inequities can be further entrenched by restricting access to funding, research opportunities, and decision-making influence

at the individual level. Temporary positions often held by early-career researchers⁷ were frequently mentioned as being affected by recent policy changes.

An urgent call from 294 ocean scientists worldwide

To ensure continued progress, we urge IOC/UNESCO Member States, the Executive Secretary, the Decade Coordination Unit, and Decade-related institutions, individually and through UNOC3 and the IOC Assembly, to reaffirm and safeguard inclusivity as a foundational goal of the Ocean Decade (Figure 2) by:

Figure 2. The Ocean Decade has committed to "leaving no one behind" and has made significant progress towards gender, generation, geography, and knowledge systems diversity. To support the Decade's capacity and resilience

towards safeguarding these commitments, continued efforts are needed to dismantle systemic barriers to unevenly distributed capacity and empowering underrepresented groups in ocean science.

1) Establishing an Ocean Decade working group to evaluate challenges and devise strategies to dismantle structural barriers to evenly distributed capacity across geographies, generations, genders, and knowledge systems.

The implementation of such a working group, facilitated by the Decade Coordination Unit and tasked with addressing systemic inequities, requires simultaneously addressing immediate needs and vulnerabilities while working towards a legacy that endures beyond 2030.

The ocean science community must invest in lasting systems of inclusion that create resilience and capacities to uphold and safeguard the Ocean Decade's commitments. This means policies must actively promote the inclusion of diverse perspectives in global ocean science and governance, ensuring that those most affected by marine challenges will be able to actively respond to the challenges through knowledge co-production and inclusive decision-making processes. The Ocean Decade's decentralized coordination, combined with broad participation, can help buffer political shifts. Broadening participation, for instance, requires Decade Actions to demonstrate the development of in-country partnerships and community leadership across all project stages¹¹. Open conversations and collaborative processes across scales can help establish a culture in which Decade Actions and National Decade Committees inform and work together on ocean literacy, early-career engagement, community leadership, and capacity-sharing, which can help rebalance power within global ocean governance, particularly amid adverse political climates.

In parallel, there is a need to evaluate the immediate impacts of anti-DEI policy-making on underrepresented groups and to develop appropriate mitigation strategies. Building on the ongoing assessment of DEI in Decade Actions and guided by open consultation, such evaluations could

help ensure that actions align with the operational principles set out in the Vision 2030 process⁵, while also addressing the unique challenges faced by different underrepresented groups.

Decade Actions can center inclusivity through transparent, co-designed processes, open reflection, and monitoring of measurable indicators. Of all submitted Decade Actions, 48.3% indicated capacity development as a priority (Figure 1). Decade Actions that enhance the capacity of, are co-led by, or build lasting relationships with underrepresented ocean researchers in leadership roles, such as the Deep Ocean Observing Strategy, Heirs to Our Ocean, or Ocean Voices already exist; more of those are needed. At the Ocean Decade level, policies that mandate diverse representation across gender, generation, geography, and knowledge systems, and eliminate harmful practices such as parachute or colonial science, are essential for holding all partners accountable. These policies must also be supported by open and critical reflection on positionality and power dynamics to promote lasting and meaningful change¹⁶.

2) Committing to empower underrepresented groups in ocean science through increased funding, capacity development, and targeted actions to promote inclusivity.

We call on Heads of State and Member State representatives, to create resilience and capacities to safeguard the pledge to ‘leave no one behind’ and support IOC/UNESCO to make inclusivity a clear and enforceable standard for the Ocean Decade.

The Member States, the Executive Secretary, and the Ocean Decade Alliance also play a central role in mobilizing and directing funding to SDG 14a for capacity development initiatives that prioritise underserved and underrepresented groups. Commitments made at UNOC3 must include the allocation of substantial resources directed towards developing equitable funding mechanisms

that help diversify ocean science and observation. In particular, funding should be dedicated to communities and regions with the least scientific and institutional capacity, as identified by the proposed Decade working group and the [Global Ocean Science Report](#). Funding initiatives, such as [OceanMatcher](#), could be made accessible to researchers from underrepresented communities and regions at the pre-application stage, helping them to overcome the financial barriers of early project development and endorsement (i.e., the 5% minimum funding requirement for Decade programmes).

Ocean science can empower communities to take active leadership roles in scientific and policy discussions, challenging power imbalances that have historically shaped the field. Achieving this goal requires nurturing diverse ocean knowledge through literacy efforts and capacity development to strengthen the autonomous scientific capabilities of underrepresented communities. Funding strategies must explicitly foster equitable partnerships and transfer of technologies and resources, driven by local priorities to ensure contextual relevance and long-term impact. For instance, building on the Ocean Decade's Latin American and Caribbean clearing-house mechanism, alongside facilitating North-South and South-South interaction, can expand collaboration to countries with complementary marine technology capacities¹⁷.

As the UN Ocean Decade reaches its midpoint, it must *leave no one behind* by embedding equity, inclusive participation, and justice across all facets of ocean science. This means enhancing institutional capacity and resilience to safeguard commitments and recent gains, while also establishing measurable and enforceable standard, inclusive funding pathways, and co-designed research agendas that meaningfully engage those most affected by ocean change. The Ocean Decade's capacity to realize the "Ocean We Want" will ultimately hinge on how effectively these principles are embedded within its views, structures, and practices.

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References

1. Bennett, N. J. *et al.* Environmental (in)justice in the Anthropocene ocean. *Marine Policy* **147**, 105383 (2023).
2. Spalding, A. K. *et al.* Engaging the tropical majority to make ocean governance and science more equitable and effective. *npj Ocean Sustain* **2**, 1–4 (2023).
3. Basurto, X. *et al.* Illuminating the multidimensional contributions of small-scale fisheries. *Nature* **637**, 875–884 (2025).
4. Cheung, W. W. L. *et al.* Climate change exacerbates nutrient disparities from seafood. *Nat. Clim. Chang.* **13**, 1242–1249 (2023).
5. Bassan, N., Flamand, A. & Clausen, A. Developing the ambition for action in the Ocean Decade to 2030. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* **82**, fsae195 (2025).
6. de Vos, A. *et al.* Towards equity and justice in ocean sciences. *npj Ocean Sustain* **2**, 1–10 (2023).
7. Satterthwaite, E. V. *et al.* Global priorities for ocean sustainability from Early Career Ocean Professionals. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* **82**, fsae201 (2025).
8. Bernard, R. E. & Cooperdock, E. H. G. No progress on diversity in 40 years. *Nature Geosci* **11**, 292–295 (2018).
9. Hofstra, B. *et al.* The Diversity–Innovation Paradox in Science. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **117**, 9284–9291 (2020).
10. Kaikkonen, L. *et al.* Fostering diversity, equity, and inclusion in interdisciplinary marine science. *npj Ocean Sustain* **3**, 1–8 (2024).
11. Polejack, A. *et al.* Hope for an accessible ocean: Blue justice and ocean science diplomacy central to the outcome of the UN Decade of Ocean Science. *Marine Policy* **176**, 106639 (2025).
12. Smallhorn-West, P. *et al.* Why human rights matter for marine conservation. *Front. Mar. Sci.* **10**, (2023).
13. Hampton-Smith, M., Gurney, G. G. & Cinner, J. E. A systematic review of equity perceptions and outcomes in marine conservation. *Biological Conservation* **289**, 110395 (2024).
14. Claudet, J. *et al.* Advancing ocean equity at the nexus of development, climate and conservation policy. *Nat Ecol Evol* **8**, 1205–1208 (2024).
15. Gattuso, J.-P., *et al.* US federal cuts threaten international ocean science and diplomacy. *Nat Ecol Evol*, 1–2 (2025).
16. Harden-Davies, H. *et al.* Capacity development in the Ocean Decade and beyond: Key questions about meanings, motivations, pathways, and measurements. *Earth System Governance* **12**, 100138 (2022).
17. Polejack, A. & Coelho, L. F. Ocean Science Diplomacy can Be a Game Changer to Promote the Access to Marine Technology in Latin America and the Caribbean. *Front. Res. Metr. Anal.* **6**, (2021).

Supplementary information

Table S1. Supplemental estimates of vulnerability to [anti-DEI policy-making](#).

Statement in text	Source / calculation
<p>“1 in 3 global ocean science publications are vulnerable to anti-DEI policy-making”</p>	<p>“At the country level, USA is the greatest producer of ocean basin research (Fig. 2), having more than doubled its output since 2000.” Source: Potter, R.W.K., Pearson, B.C., 2023. Assessing the global ocean science community: understanding international collaboration, concerns and the current state of ocean basin research. npj Ocean Sustain 2, 1–12. https://doi.org/10.1038/s44183-023-00020-y</p>
<p>“1 in 5 Decade Actions are vulnerable to anti-DEI policy-making”</p>	<p>In January 2025 the total number of endorsed Decade Actions was 648, those with lead institutions in the United States accounted for 115 Decade Actions (17.7%). Source: https://oceanexpert.org/document/29188</p>

Table S2. Two hundred fifty-two signatories to the statement “**Leave No One Behind in the UN Ocean Decade**”. Thirty-two signatories’ names are not disclosed in the table to protect their safety and to minimize any concerns regarding potential institutional repercussions. We acknowledge their valuable support and wish to recognize their contributions while respecting their need for anonymity. Signatories contributed to the revisions, the final version was published as a preprint here: [TBA]

This article reflects the opinions of the authors and signatories, and not those of their affiliated institutions.

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Table S3. Cosignatories survey questions used in analysis.

Question number	Question
9.	Do you have any concerns about how the U.S. and related anti-DEI policies may affect the ocean science (community) and Ocean Decade? If yes, please describe.
10.	Have you or your work been directly or indirectly impacted by the U.S. anti-DEI or related policies? If yes, please explain how.